

Synthesis and Evaluation of some 2-, 4- and 2,4-Di-substituted-6-methylpyrimidine Derivatives for Antimicrobial Activity

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The reaction of 2-amino-4-chloro-, 4-amino-2-chloro- and 2,4-dichloro-6-methylpyrimidines with primary aromatic amines under acidic conditions is presented. 2-, and 4- ω -substituted-thioureido-6-methylpyrimidines were synthesised via the reaction of 2-amino- and 4-amino-6-methylpyrimidine derivatives with arylisocyanates. Six compounds were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity and most of them showed a moderate activity against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *A. niger*.

SUBSEQUENT to the observation that diverse biological activities are associated with various substituted pyrimidines¹⁻⁵, some 6-methyl derivatives of the general formulae (A) and (B) were found to exhibit antimicrobial, fungicidal and insecticidal activities⁶⁻¹⁰.

Compounds comprising the thiourea moiety have a wide range of antimicrobial as well as many other pharmacological properties¹¹⁻¹³. In view of these findings and in continuation of our work on substituted-6-methylpyrimidines, we undertook to synthesise and evaluate the antimicrobial activity of some of the title compounds. The sequence of the reaction followed for the preparation of the designed compounds is summarised in Scheme 1.

2,4-Dichloro-6-methylpyrimidine (1) was prepared by applying Hilbert and Johnson's conditions to 6-methyl-2-thiouracil¹⁴. Reacting 1 with ethanolic ammonia, following the method of Behrend¹⁵, afforded a mixture of two isomers, viz. 2-amino-4-chloro-6-methylpyrimidine (3A) and 4-amino-2-chloro-6-methylpyrimidine (3B) in 60 and 40% yields, respectively, which were separated by fractional crystallisation. Derivatives having the general formulas (2a-d), (4a-c), and (6a-j) were synthesised via the condensation of 1, 3B and 3A, under acidic conditions, with the appropriate primary amines, respectively.

Fusing a mixture of equimolar proportions of 2-amino-4-chloromethylpyrimidine and anthranilic acid afforded the designed condensation product,

Scheme 1

viz. 2-amino-4-(*o*-carboxyanilino)-6-methylpyrimidine (9) whose structure was established based on chemical, analytical and spectral evidences. It underwent the characteristic chemical reactions of both carboxylic acids and primary aromatic amines. This intermediate was further cyclised by heating with sulphuric acid to give 5*H*-1-imino-3-methylpyrimidino [6, 1*b*] quinazolin-10-one (10). Supporting evidences for the structure (10) were provided. The product was found to lack a free carboxyl group. The microanalytical and ir spectral data were in agreement with the cyclised structure. In the mass spectrum, the parent ion (*m/z* 226) and the next most abundant peaks (*m/z* 199, 186, 185 and 146) were observed.

When a mixture of 2-amino-4-chloro-6-methylpyrimidine (3A) and the appropriate arylisothiocyanate was heated in dioxane for 48 h, the starting materials were recovered unchanged. Likewise, refluxing the reactants in dry acetone in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 , did not enhance results. Nevertheless, the thioureido derivatives, (7*a*–*c*), were obtained by fusing the reactants at 120° for 6 h. The nucleophilicity of the amino group in position-2 is reported^{17, 18} to be increased by the presence of electron-donating groups at the 4- or/ and 6-position. Consequently, 2-amino-4-anilino-6-methylpyrimidine (6*c*) was prepared and reacted with certain isothiocyanates when the respective 2-thioureido derivatives (8*a* and *b*) were given by refluxing in dioxane for 6 h only. On the other hand, heating an equimolar mixture of (3B) and the appropriate isothiocyanate in dioxane for 16 h or fusing at 120° for 3 h, afforded the beseeched products (5*a* and *b*).

Antimicrobial activity: The antimicrobial activity of the compounds (4*c*, 6*a*, *f*, *g* and *j*) was tested against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *Neisseria*, *Candida albicans*, *E. coli* and *Aspergillus niger* by the disc-agar-diffusion method²¹ with 50 μ l of a 0.005% solution in DMSO. Compound 6*a* showed moderate activity against *B. subtilis*, while compounds 4*c* and 6*f* were found to be active against *B. subtilis* and *A. niger*. Antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli* was exhibited by 6*g*. Compound 6*j* showed no action at all.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were run in KBr using Beckman Acculab-6 and Pye-Unicomp SP 1100 spectrometers. A Varian A-60 was used for pmr spectra. All spectra were run in deuterodimethyl sulphoxide- d_6 or deuteriochloroform- d_1 with tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. Mass spectra were measured on a Finnegan 4023 instrument. Microanalyses were performed at the Microanalytical Center, Cairo University, Egypt.

Physical and analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

2,4-Disubstituted-amino-6-methylpyrimidines (2*a*–*f*): The general procedure is illustrated for the preparation of 2,4-di(3,4-dimethylanilino)-6-methylpyrimidine (2*c*). A mixture of 2,4-dichloro-6-methylpyrimidine (1.6 g, 0.01 mol) and 3,4-dimethylaniline (2 g, 0.02 mol) was refluxed in hydrochloric acid solution (1 : 1, 25 ml) for 5 h. After cooling, 10% sodium hydroxide solution was added until the solution became neutral. The separated product was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol to give 2*c* as HCl, (85%), m.p. 245–46° (Found : N, 15.0. $C_{21}H_{25}ClN_4$ calcd. for : N, 15.2%); ν_{max} 3 320–3 200 (NH) and 3 020–2 890 (CH, arom. and aliph.) and 830–810 cm^{-1} (arom. CH wag.).

2-Amino-4-substituted-amino-6-methylpyrimidines (6*a*–*j*): The general procedure is presented for the preparation of 2-amino-4-(2,4-dimethylanilino)-6-methylpyrimidine (6*d*). A mixture of 3A (1.4 g, 0.01 mol), 2,4-dimethylaniline (2 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrochloric acid solution (1 : 1, 25 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The mixture was then neutralised with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and the separated solid filtered, crystallised from benzene to give 6*d* in almost quantitative yield, m.p. 218–19° (Found : C, 68.7; H, 7.4; N, 24.1. $C_{13}H_{16}N_4$ calcd. for : C, 68.48; H, 7.0; N, 24.5%); δ (DMSO- d_6), 2.2 (3H s), 2.26 (3H, s), 2.46 (3H, s), 5.68 (1H, s), 5.88 (2H, s), 7.1 (3H, m) and 8.22 (1H, s).

2-Amino-4-*o*-carboxyanilino-6-methylpyrimidine (9): To 9 (2 g), concentrated sulphuric acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture heated for 1 h at 100°. The solution was then cooled, diluted with cold water (10 ml) and neutralised by concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from benzene to give 10 (2 g, 90%), m.p. 160–61° (Found : C, 63.7; H, 5.0; N, 24.4. $C_{13}H_{10}N_4O$ calcd. for : C, 63.7; H, 4.4; N, 24.8%), Found : 226. calcd. for MW : 266; ν_{max} 3 300, 3 240 (two NH), 3 100, 2 980 (CH, arom. and aliph.) and 1 700 cm^{-1} (C=O).

4-Chloro-2-(ω -arylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidines (7*a*–*c*): The general procedure is illustrated for the preparation of 4-chloro-2-(ω -phenylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidine (7*a*). A mixture of 3A (1.4 g, 0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.4 g, 0.01 mol) was fused at 120° for 6 h. The resulting solid product was crystallised from ethanol to afford 7*a* (80%), m.p. 90–91° (Found : C, 51.5; H, 4.0; Cl, 12.5. $C_{13}H_{11}ClN_4S$ calcd. for : C, 51.7; H, 3.9; Cl, 12.8%); ν_{max} 3 400–3 250 (NH), 3 030–2 950 (CH, arom. and aliph.), 1 640–1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N and C=C) and 1 400–1 300 (C=S).

4-Anilino-2-(ω -arylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidines (8*a*, *b*): The general procedure is illustrated for the preparation of 4-anilino-2-(ω -*p*-tolylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidine (8*b*). A mixture of 6*c* (1 g, 0.005 mol) and *p*-tolylisothiocyanate (0.7 g, 0.005 mol) in dioxane (15 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The solvent was distilled under vacuum and the residue crystallised from ethanol to give 8*b* (~85%), m.p. 110–11° (Found : C, 65.5; H, 5.2. $C_{19}H_{19}N_4S$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.* no.	Yield** %	M.p.*** °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				C	H	N
2a	85	260–61 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₄	68.0 (68.8)	6.0 (6.5)	15.2 (15.2)
2b	85	258–59 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₄	68.9 (68.8)	6.1 (6.5)	—
2d	80	225–26 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄	75.8 (75.9)	7.0 (7.2)	16.5 (16.8)
2e	85	170–72 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₄ O ₂	—	—	19.7 (14.0)
2f	80	220–21 ^a	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂	—	—	26.2 (26.7)
4a	—	290–91 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	58.8 (58.7)	6.3 (6.4)	21.1 (21.2)
4b ^e	—	275–76 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	58.7 (58.7)	6.1 (6.4)	—
6a	—	280–81 ^a	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ O	39.2 (39.5)	5.5 (5.5)	—
6b	—	255–56 ^c	C ₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ S	30.5 (30.7)	4.7 (4.7)	—
6d	—	187–88 ^d	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄	68.5 (68.4)	6.7 (7.0)	—
6e	—	207–8 ^d	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄	68.4 (68.4)	6.7 (7.0)	—
6f	—	202–3 ^b	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ O	55.8 (55.6)	5.7 (6.1)	—
6g	—	298–93 ^c	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ F ₂	—	—	21.1 (20.9)
6h	—	300–1 ^b	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ClN ₄	50.0 (50.5)	5.1 (5.0)	29.0 (29.5)
6i	—	262–3 ^d	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O	54.5 (54.8)	5.5 (5.9)	—
7b	—	186–87 ^c	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ S	—	—	18.8 (19.1)
7c ^f	—	175–76 ^c	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₄ S	53.3 (53.3)	4.6 (4.4)	18.8 (19.1)

* Compds. 2a, 2b, 2e, 4a, 6b and 6f as hydrochloride salt, Time of reflux (h) for 2a, 2b and 2e–5, for 2d and 2f=6, for 4a=4, for 4b=3. Quantitative yield obtained for compds. 2a, 2b and 2d–i. *** Solvent of crystallisation: ^a aqueous ethanol, ^b benzene–petroleum ether, ^c ethanol, ^d benzene. ^e $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 250 and 3 100 (NH₂ and NH), 3 100–2 800 (CH, arom. and aliph.) and 1 650–1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=N and C=C), ^f $\nu_{\max}$ 3 400–3 250 (NH), 3 030–2 950 (CH, arom. and aliph.), 1 640–1 620 (C=N and C=C) and 1 400–1 300 (C=S).

calcd. for: C, 65.3; H, 5.4%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 370, 3 220 (NH), 3 100 (CH, arom.), 2 950 (CH, aliph.), 1 600, 1 580 (C=N and C=C) and 810 cm⁻¹ (CH, bending of *p*-disubstituted-benzene).

4-Anilino-2-(*o*-phenylthioureido)-6-methylpyridine (8a) was prepared adopting the same procedure mentioned for the preparation of 8b. 8a was obtained 85% in yield, m.p. 95–96° (Found: C, 64.8; H, 4.8; S, 10.0. C₁₁H₁₁N₄S calcd. for: C, 64.7; H, 4.8; S, 9.6%).

4-Amino-2-arylamino-6-methylpyrimidines (4a–c): The general procedure is presented by the preparation of 4c. A mixture of 3B (1.4 g, 0.01 mol) and *p*-aminoacetophenone (1.4 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in hydrochloric acid solution (1 : 1, 25 ml) for 3 h. The mixture was then neutralised by 10% sodium hydroxide solution and the separated solid crystallised from ethanol to give 4c in an almost quantitative yield, m.p. 98–9° (Found: C, 64.5; H, 6.0. C₁₁H₁₁N₄O calcd. for: C, 64.5; H, 5.8%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 250 and 3 100 (NH₂ and NH), 3 100–2 800 (CH, arom. and aliph.), 1 660 (C=O), 1 650–1 580 cm⁻¹ (C=N and C=C).

2-Chloro-4-(*o*-arylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidines (5a, b): The compounds were prepared by two methods which are illustrated for the preparation of 2-chloro-4-(*o*-phenylthioureido)-6-methylpyrimidine (5a).

Method A: A mixture of 3B (1.43 g, 0.01 mol) and phenylisothiocyanate (1.3 g, 0.01 mol) in dioxane (15 ml) was refluxed for 16 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and the separated compound crystallised from ethanol to afford 5a (70%), m.p. 180–81°.

Method B: A mixture of equimolar amounts of 3B and phenylisothiocyanate was fused at 120° for 3 h. The solid mass was then crystallised from ethanol to give 5a (60%), m.p. and m.m.p. 180–81°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 350 (NH), 3 100, 2 590 (CH, arom. and aliph.), 1 350 (C=S) and 750 cm⁻¹ (arom. CH wag).

On applying method A, 5b was obtained in 68% yield, while method B afforded the same compound in 52%, m.p. and m.m.p. 198–99° (Found: N, 18.9; S, 11.1. C₁₁H₁₁ClN₄S calcd. for: N, 19.2; S, 11.0%).

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